

A Research Study to Explore Learning English Language Through Literature ...

A Research Study to Explore Learning English Language Through Literature from University Students of Education Department

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Abstract

In this research, its investigated that students learn English language through literature or piece of literary work help students to learn language easily. In this research mainly undergraduate book of English is focused because there are many literary pieces of writings which help students to learn language easily. In the department of education English is being taught as a compulsory subject and there are many lessons in that book which cover English literature genres such as short stories, literary articles and biographies etc. These genres help us to enhance our vocabulary and syntactical structure.

Keywords: Literature, Language, Education, Learning, Stories, Vocabulary, Syntax

INTRODUCTION

The aim of the research is to use English literature in English classroom at the university level students who belongs the department of Education various genres of English literature such as epic, drama, poetry and fiction in which are available in the English for Undergraduates compulsory courses. Hişmanoğlu (2005) has emphasized the use of literature as popular techniques for the sake of teaching basic English language skills such as listening, speaking and reading, writing, and language domains such as words, grammar, and pronunciation. The main purpose of the study has to focusing on the use of English literature in the development of the four language skills of university English students. The use of literary references in a foreign language or in the teaching of another language is then widely discussed. In addition, the research focuses on words and grammar. Finally, it can increase opportunities to add literature further to the curriculum.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

1. To explore necessity of English literature in developing language skills in Compulsory English.
2. To investigate the effect of teaching language through literature from English for undergraduates.

A Research Study to Explore Learning English Language Through Literature ...

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. How English literature is necessary for the development English language skills of the students in the universities?
2. How can language teaching effect on learning language through literature?

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Recently English literature became an important component as well as source of authoritative in the text of the language courses. It is providing reality of life in the content and is a useful addition to such content. Carter “has confirmed that written texts are real texts to which we can directly respond. There has been a heated debate among language teachers about how, when, where and why literature is included in the ESL / EFL curriculum”(1986, p.15). “Many teachers find the usage of English literature in the teaching of English language as an interesting and worrying method In addition, there are many language learners who very much interested reading novels, poems and short stories and fictionetc” (Sage 1987, p. 1).

PARADIGM OF RESEARCH

Today, learning English through literature is shifting between two different stories. The most obvious example is that it is based on standards set by language and educational principles and is related to language skills. On the other hand, the rising principles of allegorical linguistics and pedagogy relate to local conditions, and this position itself criticizes the political significance of ELT through literature. The interaction between these two stories creates tensions where they have an interface, i.e. what language (what language to teach), what method (how) and for what reason (why) to teach (Kostoulas, 2010).

Language is an integral part of human life and without language, there is no communication; “English has become an essential language for people to communicate around the world. In a globalized world, English proficiency can offer many opportunities. Good command of English allows a small number of learners to enjoy their lives and careers”.(2014 R. Roshid& Webb, 2013, p.45 ; Ehsan,2011, p.54,).

Under the influence of the language, psychology, education, and political perspectives produced by the “mixture of language, theory, perception, and experience,” the theory of language learning has changed over time” (Hall and Cook, 2012, p.272). it is Development of new ways and new methods but it is a difficult work for foreign language teaching teachers.” Communication language pedagogy is satisfied with the usage of reality of the life situations when using language as much as can be. The structural exercises has been in the usage in the audio language ways which build the process of teaching tedious” (Gangula, 2015,p.43). Literature is a major component in translating grammar. “ the literary books are in the priority to use language for reading and translation, and usage as models of excellent for writing and models for principles grammar” (Duff &Milli 1990, p.67). Over the past two decades, literature has been seen as an effective tool in foreign language teaching and curricula (Babaei and Yahya, 2014). Duff and Milli (1990) also pointed out that over the past two decades that the usage of English literature is seen as a valuable resource in English language education.

Reading an entire novel in another language can be very stressful and overwhelming. Such

A Research Study to Explore Learning English Language Through Literature ...

texts firmly capture the mind of the reader and create a scale for language analysis (Gangula, 2015).

Literature can help students develop explanatory skills. It is an excellent tool to improve students' understanding of meaning and its ability to interpret (Gangula, 2015 and Lazarus, 1993). Language class literature provides learners with the opportunity to comment on themselves and make logical statements. By using written texts, language lessons may be made brighter and more impressive (Violetta, 2015, p.78). Further, it may play an important aspect in the process of translation of grammar. "Read and translate documents in the target language and use them as samples of excellent in writing and the embodiment of principles grammar" (Duff & Milli 1990, p. 3). It also introduces students to global issues. According to a study by Slater (1990), diverse and very diverse literary material is proposed in the literature in response to evolving human problems (Gangula, 2015). The unified teaching method allows students to acquire skills at all levels in the context of ordinary literature. More surprising to students is reading real books instead of old stories.

However, many linguists ask that how and why English literature has been included in English language courses. There are any language teachers that are facing many difficulties in teaching language through literature. "First, it is very rare to use appropriate textbooks for language teaching through literature. Secondly, there is no important basic work in the field of language training and literature. Third, no important goals were seen to explain the scope and importance of English literature in English language courses" (Babae and Yahya, 2014, P.68). This research would be helpful in policy making for the curriculum developers as well as teachers and students and in order to understand the gains of literature in improving the skills English language in the university.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature has been studied to varying degrees in many countries / regions, but more recently it has received a lot of attention in EFL classes (Kaşlıoğlu & Ersin, 2018). In recent years, the usage of texts of literature in the teaching of abroad languages is increased significantly. The role of literature in language courses in 1960–1980 was questioned. The methods of the 1970s and early 1980s discussed the methods and emphasized the practicality of English. In the 1980s, bent of mind for language and literature and education returned. It is a fact that literature is known as a valuable language learning tool began twenty years ago (Hall, 2005 Duff & Milli, 1990). It can be compatible with the communication methods because it maintains real communication conditions in second language teaching (Sons & Fernandez, 1997).

The written text must be taken with the learner's needs, life experience and goals, further its language level and cultural background. A research study by Koli and Slater (1987), work should not exceed students' literacy. Interest, charm and relevance are all important.

Coley and Slater (1990) and Milli (1989) listed four main reasons that force language teachers to use literature in the classroom. "These are valuable authentic materials, rich culture, rich language and personal involvement. In addition, other factors such as globalization, randomness, personal significance, change, interest, economy, consulting tact, and difficulties are also full of power resources in the class".

Carter (1991) has developed three models that are used in the literature, "cultural models,

A Research Study to Explore Learning English Language Through Literature ...

language models, and models of personal growth". Each model represents a vary trend in methods and class teaching. He also pointed out that literature is essential for personal development.

Growth is a way of personal development in which students become attached to written texts. Through the literature, students learn to accept and evaluate cultural models. This is especially true for student-centered imitation.

Duff and Millie (1992) suggest many interesting activities for teachers, teacher trainees, and teachers interested in using written text in ELT. The main purpose of the Mili method is to use written text as a tool to speed up language operations. Demigo (2006) pointed out that literary books are known as an important in levels are three; "linguistics, methodology, and stimulation".

Hilton, Osmany, and Thomas (1998) has described benefits of the novels in the education: "they are stimulating learners and develop imagination, and build ability to resolve problems, and further ability to develop their speaking and language of written. It is comprehensive process of learning, so learners may easily participate in the reading process faster". And, according to David Hill, (1993) proposed a three-dimensional approach: awareness raising, text interaction, and post-production. This method gives students more information and motivation in order to make learning of the language easy. The author Duncan (2005) believes that literature, because of its educational value, is a real substance for language learning and encourages interaction on the basis of social values of different learners. The general language has changed according to geography, vary of social circumstances, social conditions are different as well as occupations. In this context, the literature introduces learners to different language options such as society, regional dialects, professional languages, idioms, etc. Therefore, the literature incorporates sociolinguistic aspects into target language learning (Shahid, 2016) and learning. (Carter & Long, 1991; Wan, 2009; 2011). This study developed a "theoretical framework for the study of language learning through the literature," which focused on the various benefits of the study and explored these features.

RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

However, many linguists ask why and how literature has been embodied in language courses. There are many language teachers are facing many difficulties in teaching language through literature. First of all it is a considerable thing that there is very rare usage of appropriate textbooks for language teaching through literature. On other hand, there is nothing important basic work in the field of language training and literature. Furthermore on third point it has no important goals that has been found in order to explain the importance of literature in language courses (Babae and Yahya, 2014). This research would be helpful policy makers, curriculum experts, students, and teachers understand the benefits of literature in improving the language skills of the University English students.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This framework represents the relationship between textual work of language and literature learning, which is the reason for the usage of literature work in English classrooms. It continues to show teaching and learning methods as well as the development of the

A Research Study to Explore Learning English Language Through Literature ...

students in learning language skills. This conceptual frame also focuses on student choice, and learning proper and effective language and literature through teaching. There are gains of learning and teaching through the process learning in various ways of literature which short stories, poems, novels and drama etc. there are many issues regarding language teachers that they face many in teaching English language through literature. In this research the researchers intend to study use of English literature for the development of students through language skills.

METHODOLOGY

The nature of this research is qualitative because all the aspects of qualitative research would be followed. In order to make things easy and convenient the conducting research and carrying on research study as a researcher would mainly collect data through open-ended questionnaires from the respondents. These methods of collecting data through questionnaire of open-ended and interview based on semi-structured schedule which would be conducted from students as well as teachers.

DATA COLLECTION METHOD

There are various ways to collect data but in this research data would be collected through interviews and questionnaires. Creswell (2008), "the data would be collected in written and developed into data groups and topics, combined with reports, and generalized for explanation". As data the way of collection of data and analysis of the data is concerned, the researcher would use the checklist for clarifying in discussion with the interviewee. Researcher would make assure that the data is accurately coded as well as analyzed. And, the approach of theme has been applied for the analysis of the collected data and the research in-depth.

SAMPLE/PARTICIPANTS AND INSTRUMENT(S)

There would be thirty (30) students studying English at universities are selected with determination. There would be six teachers would be intentionally selected and they also teach at universities. To facilitate the survey, open data is collected through interviews from participants. This study develops open ended questionnaires as well as semi-structured interview which would helpful to collect data. The open ended questionnaire and interview method would be based on such questions that are about learning language through literature.

RATIONALE OF THE QUALITATIVE RESEARCH METHOD

This research is based on semi-structured interviews as well as open ended questions that lead to mixed method but in the research when we are going to follow observation of the participants of the research and examination of the data from the literature

1. Observations e.g. participative, non-participative observations etc.
2. Examining literature review; the research that has been already conducted on the topic.
3. Critique; collecting data from the primary sources and analyzing that data.

A Research Study to Explore Learning English Language Through Literature ...

DATA ANALYSIS

The data would be analyzed on the basis of the participants' interviews and questionnaires. As interviewees' questions are mentioned that learning English language through literature is a pleasant thing and agreed that they all benefited a lot from practicing literature to improve their language skills. They have also accepted that literature is providing a resource or authoritative context, encourages language learning. "This provides authoritative examples of language use principles, and provides learners with their language, helping to improve public awareness and knowledge, develop interpreting and analytical skills, and improve vocabulary". (Gangula, 2015, p.56). In the end, interviewees would be stated that their main concern with English language proficiency is oral proficiency. He agreed that reading one written text in one of the four language skills would be better. In addition, the inclusion of literature in the ELT classroom is considered a useful process because "it promotes students' language development; appreciate of various cultures, personal participating, and personal development" (Carter & Long, 1991). Bobby and Yahya (2014) added that written works can help students stimulate their imagination and emotions.

There are many students recognize that literary text can play an important way in improving in the skills of the language. They all got benefit from the practice of literary works and thus improved their language skills. He also said that learning English through literature is very interesting. Most importantly, learning is irrelevant. They learn through literature unconsciously, without learning pressures. According to a study by Obidet (1997), literature can enable students to master native English language skills, as to describe their thoughts in proper English and learn the qualities of English in modern age, and how to communicate using the English-speaking system. , See how the idiom is expressed. Be creative, critical and analytical and know how, clear, accurate and proficient in English. Literature can also help students demonstrate interpreting skills (Lazarus, 1993; Gangula, 2015). It is a fact that literature may be used as an effective and full of inspiration way to learn English that is second language to learn (Shahid, 2016). Alam and Ashraf-ul-Zaman (2018) pointed out that context is playing a very important role among teachers reading lectures and books.

In addition, most of them believe that a good knowledge of reading and literature is depending on skills of grammar. They are preferring the grammar rather than the literary language learning process because they believe that if basic grammar is converted directly into literature without sufficient knowledge, learners will have great difficulty.

In addition to academic books, most students read literary books, and their favorite novels, novels, and science fiction are such literary works. Jowett (2017) also found that students looked at major genres of literature to combine short stories, novels, and realistic text, and different types of texts. They have a positive response to reading literature in their own language of land because it helps them understand it. There are interviewees based pointed out that written works read in their mother tongue are easier to read. They have a positive response to reading native language literature. It is also helping to understand the meaning of light. Slater (1987) pointed out that the use of the target language helps to cope with the cause with nonverbal or limited language skills.

According to the interviewees, literature can be the main source of learning the language of communication. This can make the course more productive and interesting. Responsible

A Research Study to Explore Learning English Language Through Literature ...

teachers have looked at different methods and techniques for different topics and student needs. Interviewees engage in discussions, role-plays, open discussions, discussions, write creative assignments and place them in the classroom, such as reading literature, discussing in English, discussing with friends or teachers in English, watching English movies, watching programs, singing, speaking, etc. Ashraf Al-Zaman ET, may God be merciful to him. (2010) also found that English teachers use many useful collaborative techniques to enhance the teaching process. Slater's (1987) method suggests that group activities help students find their own reactions to the literature. "The communication literary text in the literature is considered a powerful tool to understand a method and source of communication with each other according to different situations and different perspectives". The choice of written texts must take into account the teaching methods and techniques used in language teaching, students' language skills, interests, age, gender, etc., so that students are not burdened with inappropriate material. Sutton (1998) explained that literature can open a horizon of possibilities, allowing students to ask questions, explain, connect, and explore. Violetta (2015) also suggested "transforming the language class of literary textbooks into a lively space".

KEY ETHICAL MEASURES

In this research the participants' security and privacy is fully confidential, nothing would be done without their consent. The respect and dignity of the research participants and research members would be on high priority. And, data would be ensured without any artificiality and fake addition in the data. There is no exaggeration in the research questions and research objectives and these all are based on the research topic. Research limitations would be followed strictly.

CONCLUSION

Therefore, it's concluded that the students of department of education learning English through literature from different literary stories of the English in the book of English for undergraduates. This research has been conducted through different undergraduate students who desired to learn English through literature is more convenient and easy to learn because it enhances vocabulary and structure of the students.

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A Research Study to Explore Learning English Language Through Literature ...

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